

E-payment System: Characteristics and Features

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CITATION: Lohar, Anil; Gajare, Yogini and Kumar, Atul (2017), “E-payment System: Characteristics and Features”, *Siddhant Management Review*, Vol. 2, Issue 1, pp. 19-23.

ARTICLE TYPE: Review paper

ABSTRACT

The financial system is considered as a real backbone of any economy. A reliable and transparent financial system is a must for handling an increasing number of monetary transactions of the economy. The e-payment system in India becoming more popular and e-payments have witnessed an exponential growth in last few years. In this article, first attempt is made to understand the e-payments, second attempt to critically analyses characteristics of e-payment system and final attempt to find the features of the ideal electronic payment system. The article is based on exploratory research and secondary data. The data was accumulated from books, journals, magazines, websites and other published sources available. This article provides an original insight of e-payment system, characteristics of e-payment system and features of the ideal electronic payment system. The basic characteristics of e-payment system are applicability, ease of use, security, reliability, trust, scalability, convertibility, interoperability, efficiency, anonymity, traceability, and authorisation type. The features of the ideal electronic payment service are compliant, reversals, freely accessible (non-discriminatory), immediate, final, transaction amount neutral, transparent and anonymity.

KEYWORDS: Financial system, E-payment, Financial transactions, E-commerce, Digital currency, Indian economy.

1. INTRODUCTION

New monetary wants have been emerged due to e-commerce which was lacking with standard payment systems. The presence of this e-commerce has initiated different payment tools or mechanisms for completing the business transactions through internet. Therefore, the stakeholders came up with completely new strategies for electronic payments. Recognising this, just about all interested parties square measure exploring numerous forms of the electronic payment system and problems encompassing electronic payment system and digital currency.

Usually, e-payment systems could be categorised into On-line Electronic Money System, On-line MasterCard Payment, Electronic Cheque, and Cards based mostly Electronic Payment System. Every payment system has its blessings and downsides for the purchasers and merchants. Security, convenience, cost, anonymity, acceptableness, traceability, and control are some basis mandates of these new payment systems. Most of the banks have started following e-commerce supporting the e-payment system for sustaining in the hyper-competitive market. Though Indian economy is considered as a cash-driven economy, however, it is not so far away in adopting e-payment services in banking as well as a retail sector (Roy, 2015).

The financial system is considered as a real backbone of any economy. A reliable and transparent financial system is a must for handling an increasing number of monetary transactions of the economy. Here, the financial system means, banks as well as non-bank financial institutions that are offering different types of financial services to their targeted customers. Fund transfers, as well as financial clearing, are considered two prominently important services as compared to other services of

the payment system. The payment system is a key role player in enhancing the business growth, improving the financial intelligibility and supporting the reforms of the sector. The attitude and behaviour of people or customers of new payment system have been changing drastically from last two decades. The major reasons for the same are following:

1. **Increased either volume or value of transaction:** Not only the numbers but also the value of the transactions are increasing as the people are considering their financial matter most important. Because of this new phenomenon, there is a rapid growth in the activities of the financial market can be noticed around the globe and the payment generated by such activity.
2. **Technological enhancement:** From last 20 years there's an unbelievable technological improvement in banking and money sector. It's owing to the advancement of data and communication technology and big growth of net. As a result, money establishments and shoppers each have the flexibility and therefore the resource to manoeuvre funds abundant quicker through the system, at a lower value.
3. **Effect of globalisation:** As an outcome of the globalisation, many businesses have started to overcome geographical boundaries. As a result, a lot of money transactions are flowing across the countries. The corporate that has the aptitude to contour its payment mechanism is ready to trim prices and therefore succeed competitive advantage. This will be attainable solely in cross-nation payment.

Globalisation and financial revolution came with some drastic changes in developing countries in various aspects. Some of the notable changes are: new opportunities of trading and investments, changes in the consumers taste and preferences, increase in the demands of international products. Technological advancements have also played a critical role in making the world borderless. Improved communication and information technology have also provided unbelievable chances in the world economy, with the help of the Internet, counties are connected digitally. Electronic money is the outcome product of this digital convergence and also proved as electronic replacement of cash. The idea of electronic payment for trading in goods and services is not new to the world. Several schemes were offered to promote the electronic payment or payment through a computer network in late 1970's as well as early 1980's. Aristotle (384 – 322 B.C.) said that “everything must be assessed by money; for this enables men always to exchange their services and so makes society possible.”

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

In this article, a modest attempt is made:

- To understand and define the e-payment.
- To critically analyse characteristics of e-payment system.
- To find the features of the ideal electronic payment service.

3. METHODOLOGY

The article is based on exploratory research and secondary data. The data was accumulated from books, journals, magazines, websites and other published sources available. This article provides an original insight of characteristics of e-payment system and features of the ideal electronic payment service.

4. E-PAYMENT

E-payment is the “exchange of monetary value online via the Internet, private networks or a combination of it” (Majhi *et al.*, 2000). A typical e-payment transaction is where merchants collect revenue from customers when they pay for goods or services online using electronic payment methods such as Paypal. There are many risks involving conducting a payment electronically such as fraudulent activities.

Electronic-payment is an activity in which, many users can participate in reducing their risk. (Whyte, 2001). Nevertheless, e-payment does provide some benefits and convenience to customer, merchants, and banks that are involved in an electronic transaction (Anderson, 2001). Different electronic payment methods have different benefits and risks.

5. CHARACTERISTICS OF E-PAYMENT SYSTEM

Various researches are conducted in the field of electronic payment system for settling financial transactions. The characteristics of electronic payment are flexibility, security, trust, reliability, ease of use, efficiency, convertibility, and traceability can be seen in (Lynch and Lunquist, 1996; Medvinsky and Neuman 1993). The literature has listed many characteristics which are as

follows: usability, anonymity, convertibility, applicability, efficiency, authorisation type, trust, reliability, security, traceability, and scalability. However, these characteristics are mainly focusing on the technical portion of the electronic payment system which is again one part of the payment system.

There are many places where the users identify different aspects of electronic payment systems when the transaction takes place, for example, convertibility and applicability. However, there are other characteristics that are experienced indirectly, but still, have an influence on users. To demonstrate this variation, the depicted attributes of electronic payment can be segregated on those that are recognised by users directly and those that are visible to users. Direct opinion about the user related attributes is traceability, reliability, efficiency, applicability, anonymity, usability, trust, convertibility and security. Indirect perceptions about the technology linked characteristics are interoperability, scalability, divisibility and authorisation type.

The research has investigated that this division is reasonable in the respect that users really do not have an understanding and direct experience with 'indirect influence' characteristics. Further, the research found that the user-related characteristics have an immediate influence on users and, therefore, on user acceptance of electronic payment systems. Various traits of electronic payment systems are elaborated below to explain various characteristics such as technological factors, user-related factors, and political factors. They can also be transformed into requirements for a future system.

5.1. Applicability

The utility of electronic payment system depends on what the user can obtain from it. The applicability of an electronic payment mechanism is described as the amount to which it is recognised for payments. For instance, cash is accepted widely and thus has a high level of applicability. Applicability of a payment system may vary from country to country. Quite high applicability has debit cards (bank cards) and credit cards, while cheques are no longer common in several European countries.

5.2. Ease of use

Paying with an electronic payment system should not be a complex task; we will call this characteristic ease of use or usability. Usability is an important characteristic and defined as "the extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use" (ISO/DIS 9241-11.2, Part 11, 1996). Payments should be automated and done in an easy, seamless way. In such a responsible task as a payment process user should have minimum factors that make it difficult to pay or distract them.

5.3. Security

Since we have an open network system for the internet services, the security which supports the electronic commerce in particular payment systems has to be immune to attacks in the Internet conditions. For electronic cash systems, the issue of security has a special angle of counterfeiting, which means that no one should be able to produce electronic tokens on their own. Another angle is double spending; design should ensure that electronic tokens couldn't be spent twice.

5.4. Reliability

Naturally, users would like to see that system is reliable because the smooth running of an enterprise will depend on the availability of the payment infrastructure, (Medvinsky and Neuman, 1993).

5.5. Trust

It has been identified that many attributes are there in this system but trust is an essential attribute of the system (Egger, 2000). A proper demonstration is required to bring the most attributes to the system. The essential attribute is trust (Egger, 2000). Trust in this context refers to the degree of confidence that money and personal information will be safe and that parties involved will not act against user's interest. From the perspective of using a payment system people trust that payments will be conducted in a proper way, that money will not be stolen or misused. On the other hand, even if we use an imperfect system, we believe that vendors, banks and credit cards companies will not use the information against us. Another aspect of trust is that other parties should have trust in the payment systems we want to use, based on this trust they would be willing to conduct commerce.

5.6. Scalability

As the commercial use of the Internet grows, the demands placed on payment infrastructure will also increase. The payment infrastructure as a whole should be scalable, to be able to handle the addition of users and merchants, so that systems will perform normally without performance degradation (Medvinsky and Neuman, 1993). Among the least scalable systems are those that require from users and vendors purchase and installation of additional hardware; this often hampers the development of electronic cash systems.

5.7. Convertibility

Naturally, users will select payment mechanisms as financial instruments according to their needs. Numerous payment schemes have emerged up to now and we can expect new systems to appear, all providing assorted services and applications for assorted users' needs. Funds represented by one mechanism should be easily convertible into funds represented by others.

5.8. Interoperability

A payment system is interoperable if it is not dependent on one organisation, but is open and allows as many as necessarily interested parties to join. This can be achieved by means of open standards for the technology that is used. It is natural, though, that companies that implement new technologies treat them as know-how, because of the added value they create by investing in the technologies; therefore, it is not always sensible to demand interoperability. Examples of interoperable initiatives are the CAFE project, (Boly, 1994) and SEMPER project (www.semper.org).

5.9. Efficiency

There are lots of discussions on the ability of payment systems to accept "micropayments". Small payments are amounts less than a \$1; micropayments are less than several cents. Systems should be able to receive small payments without performance degradation and posing high costs of transactions, (Low *et al.* 1994). The costs per transaction should be reasonable for processing small amounts.

5.10. Anonymity

The following characteristics reflect a desire to protect one's privacy, identity, and personal information. For some transactions, identities of the parties in the transactions could be protected by anonymity. Anonymity suggests that it is not possible to discover someone's identity or to monitor an individual's spending patterns. Where anonymity is important, the cost of tracking a transaction should outweigh the value of the information that can be obtained by doing so. For an illustration, when one pays with a debit card, the purchase is registered at vendor and bank's databases. It is possible to find out what amount was paid and what actually was purchased, thus debit card payments are not anonymous. On the contrary, we can state that cash is an anonymous payment system, as there is no direct information about you personally on banknotes. There are laws in several EU countries that limit use of personal information by banks, authorities and other parties.

5.11. Traceability

Anonymity relates to the characteristic of traceability. Traceability indicated how easy it is to trace money flows, sources of funds or link spent funds to a customer via payment activities. There are lots of films (for example fast and furious) where police are able to find someone who is using credit cards in any place over the US and even worldwide. This suggests that credit cards are traceable. Anonymity and traceability are important for users as characteristics that induce trust.

5.12. Authorisation type

Another characteristic of this kind is authorisation type that is addressed in the literature as an ability of a system to perform payments not being connected to a central authority, (Asokan *et al.*, 1997, Lynch and Lundquist, 1996). Authorisation type can be offline or online. Offline authorisation type means that users of the system can exchange money not being connected to a network, without a third party as a mediator. Natural illustration for offline authorization is the exchange of cash. Some electronic payment systems, e.g. Mondex, also offer this kind of service.

6. FEATURES OF THE IDEAL ELECTRONIC PAYMENT SERVICE

- **Compliant:** Whichever domains the system must be working; it must be legally compliant with the laws and licenses.

- **Reversals:** The system should be flexible enough to the reversals that are mistreated in a payment system should not happen.
- **Freely accessible (non-discriminatory):** The electronic payment system should be available to a wide audience as possible like cash and for those people who considered not creditworthy.
- **Immediate:** It is like instead of paying cash you can simply receive an authorisation message.
- **Final:** It is like being paid with cash than having a possible disagreement with a mediator or financial organisation.
- **Transaction amount neutral:** The transaction fees are high in larger amounts as compared to smaller amounts.
- **Transparent:** The system permits the sender to see whether the recipient has received the payment or not. You can visually confirm the receipt instead of relying on some form of notification that payment was made.
- **Anonymity:** The transaction is conducted between the sender and the receiver.

7. CONCLUSION

The financial system is considered as a real backbone of any economy. A reliable and transparent financial system is a must for handling an increasing number of monetary transactions of the economy. The e-payment system in India becoming more popular and e-payments have witnessed an exponential growth in last few years. The e-payment can be explained as a typical transaction, where merchants collect revenue from customers when they pay for goods or services online using electronic payment methods such as Paypal. The basic characteristics of e-payment system are applicability, ease of use, security, reliability, trust, scalability, convertibility, interoperability, efficiency, anonymity, traceability, and authorisation type. The features of the ideal electronic payment service are compliant, reversals, freely accessible (non-discriminatory), immediate, final, transaction amount neutral, transparent and anonymity.

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